

A DFT and ab-initio study on the primary oxidation mechanism of S₂

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Abstract

The objective of the present work is to compile, test and validate a computational method that will provide thermochemical and kinetic parameters needed to develop an elementary reaction model for accurately describing the combustion of sulfur. Reactions of S₂ with oxygen were investigated using Density Functional Theory B3LYP (with several basis sets), BB1K/GTLarge and the composite ab-initio methods G2, G3, G3MP2, G3MP2B3 and CBS-QB3. In detail, using these computational methods the reactions of SO₃ → SO₂ + O^{3p}, S₂ + O₂ → 2SO, S₂ + O^{3p} → SSO and SSO → SO + S^{3p} are investigated in this study. The results have shown that final transition state structures vary significantly with the applied method and that using B3LYP as an example, large basis sets such as 6-311G+(3df,2p) are necessary for reliable results. Kinetic parameters for SO₃ dissociation to SO₂ and O are determined using canonical transition state theory. Rate constants of reaction were calculated at different computational levels and are compared with available literature. The results reported in this work are to be considered as first insight into the system and have to be improved by more accurate calculations.

Introduction

Combustion of elemental sulfur is performed in large-scale as a part of the industrial production process of sulfuric acid which is one of the world's largest-volume industrial chemicals. As such, sulfur combustion in existing facilities is technically robust and mostly designed to realize large product streams [1, 2]. Electricity generation may be carried out with the heat generated from sulfur combustion and the process is independent of encasement: Sulfur is a very cost-effective material and can be inexpensively stored outdoor under ambient conditions for long times and in large quantities [2]. In contrast, there has been relatively little research on the combustion of elemental sulfur. There are several reported studies that have focused on the oxidation of SO₂ to SO₃. Naidoo et al. have conducted an experimental kinetic study of the SO₂ + O association [3] and Jiang et al. have reported a quantum chemistry study on the reaction of SO₂ with O₃ and H₂O₂ [4]. The reactions of diatomic sulfur S₂ in the atmosphere with O, O₂ and O₃ and HO₂ have been investigated in the experimental work of Hills et al., [5] and rates of some reactions have been determined.

However, little data on the kinetic of SO₃ dissociation are available. Yilmaz et al. [6] have conducted experiments on the thermal dissociation of SO₃ in the temperature range of 1000-1400 K and have determined a rate constant for SO₃ + N₂ → SO₂ + O + N₂. In this work we compare quantum chemistry based calculated values with this experimental values of ref. [6]. As will be discussed below, we consider the results reported in this work as first insight into the system which has to be improved by more accurate calculations.

Specific Objectives

The main purpose of the present work is to compile, test and validate the performance of a computational method to assure accurate results for the rate coefficients of the combustion of elemental sulfur. The further goal is to develop a mechanism that describes the reactions in the S₂ + O₂ system on the basis of elementary reactions.

In detail, transition state structures of four reactions are calculated with the help of different DFT and ab-initio methods. One of the fundamental prerequisite is the knowledge of thermodynamic properties of the intermediate species resulting from the S₂ + O₂ reaction system and their precursors.

Computational Methods

Thermochemical and kinetic properties for sulfur compounds are estimated by several computational methods using the Gaussian 03 program suite [7, 8]. We used the hybrid density functional theory (DFT) at B3LYP/6-311G(d,p), B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p), B3LYP/6-311+G(2d,p), B3LYP/CBSB7 [9, 10, 11], B3LYP/LANL2DZ [12, 13], and BB1K/GTLarge [14, 15] level. The ab-initio methods tested in this work are G2 [16], G3 [17], G3MP2 [18], G3MP2B3 [19, 20] and CBS-QB3 [21].

Results and Discussion

Thermodynamic calculations

In this work, geometries, standard enthalpies of formation, entropies and heat capacities of reactants, products and transition state structures describing the S₂ + O₂ reactions are calculated. Calculations of standard enthalpies of formation, at the different DFT levels, and composite ab-initio methods are from use of isodesmic work reactions. Enthalpies of the transition state

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structures (TS) were obtained from the computational enthalpies of the TS structures and the calculated enthalpies of formation of the reactants and products. For all DFT calculations, zero-point energies (ZPVEs) and thermal corrections to 298.15 K are applied. Frequencies and moments of inertia are determined with each method in order to calculate the entropies and heat capacities.

The calculated enthalpies exhibit serious differences which are partially due to the geometries obtained with the different methods. Figure 1, e.g. illustrates possible geometries of S_2O_2 : The left one obtained with B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) and G3MP2B3, the middle one obtained with B3LYP/6-311+G(2d,p), BB1K/GTLarge and the right one with G2, G3 and G3MP2. Because of the diversity of results, which need to be thoroughly evaluated, these data are not used in the present study but will be available in future work. For this preliminary study we have solely focused on SO_3 , SO_2 , S_2 , SO , $OSSO$, SSO and S_2O_2 and the corresponding transition state structures.

Figure 1: Geometries calculated for S_2O_2 at **left:** B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) and G3MP2B3, **middle:** B3LYP/6-311+G(2d,p) and BB1K/GTLarge, **right:** G2, G3 and G3MP2.

Reaction of SO_3 to $SO_2 + O$

1. Reaction enthalpy

The reaction enthalpy represented as relative energy of SO_3 to the transition state structure (TS- SO_3) has been determined at different levels of calculation and is listed in Table 1. The several methods show different reaction enthalpy values. However, sort of groups with similar values can be observed.

The geometries shown in Figures 2 and 3 may explain these deviations. Two type of structures have been obtained: The first one (Figure 2) shows a S—O(1) normal double bond at 1.47 Å, while S—O(2) bond at 1.53Å is between double and single bond. The third S—O(3) bond is at 1.63 Å. The vibrations show oxygens 2 and 3 attempting to form a new bond to form O_2 and probably leave the sulfur atom. This structure has been obtained with all B3LYP calculations as well as with G3MP2B3 and the relative enthalpy is around -30 kcal mol^{-1} .

All other methods have identified a clear structure showing one oxygen atom leaving the SO_3 molecule, as illustrated in Figure 3. G3 and G3MP2 methods have found an excellent transition state structure where S—O(1) and (2) are clearly double bonded while S—O(3) is at 2.02 Å, just leaving the sulfur atom. For both methods the relative energy is situated higher than the previous structure at -18 kcal mol^{-1} .

The calculated BB1K relative energy is similar but slightly higher at -21 kcal mol^{-1} because the distance

between the leaving oxygen and the S-atom (S—O(3)) is longer with 2.19 Å.

Table 1: Relative energy of SO_3 to transition state structure TS- SO_3

$SO_3 \rightarrow TS-SO_3$		$\Delta H_{rxn} (kcal mol^{-1})$
Method-basis set	Reaction enthalpy	Bond length of transition state structure Å
B3LYP/6-311G(d,p)	-31.82	S—O (1) = 1.47
B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p)	-31.94	S—O (2) = 1.53
B3LYP/6-311G+(2d,p)	-30.41	S—O (3) = 1.63
G3MP2B3	-28.81	
B3LYP/CBSB7	-9.57	S—O (1) = 1.44
CBS-QB3	-15.96	S—O (2) = 1.44
		S—O (3) = 2.83
G2	-67.33	S—O (1) = 1.44
		S—O (2) = 1.44
		S—O (3) = 3.24
BB1K	-21.87	S—O (1) = 1.44
		S—O (2) = 1.44
		S—O (3) = 2.19
G3	-18.02	S—O (1) = 1.46
G3MP2	-18.03	S—O (2) = 1.46
		S—O (3) = 2.02
B3LYP/LANL2DZ	-45.30	-

Figure 2: Structure of TS- SO_3 -A with G3MP2B3, B3LYP/6311G(d,p), B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p), B3LYP/6-311+G(2d,p)

Figure 3: Structure of TS- SO_3 -B at CBSB7, *BB1K, CBS-QB3, *G3 and *G3MP2. *Best structures

While the S—O(3) distance increases, e.g. 2.83 Å, as obtained with CBSB7 and CBS-QB3, the transition state structures are no longer reliable because the oxygen is about to be completely free as observed with G2, in which the S—O(3) distance is 3.24 Å (see Fig. 4).

The results obtained with LANL2DZ show a totally different structure which will not be discussed in this work.

Figure 4: Structure of TS-SO3 with G2.
Imaginary frequency = $-171.3033 \text{ cm}^{-1}$

Reaction enthalpies for the dissociation reaction of SO_3 to $\text{SO}_2 + \text{O}$ assimilated to S—O bond energy in the SO_3 molecule have been determined with different levels of calculation. For each method, the bond energy (BE) is estimated as the calculated energy difference between the products and educts and converted into kcal mol^{-1} . The bond energies are listed in Table 2. According to reported enthalpies in the literature [22], the S—O bond energy (BE) is calculated to be $83.20 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$. Except for BB1K/GTLarge, the different methods listed in Table 2 result all in lower BE values. All methods including MP2 calculations (G2, G3, G3MP2, G3MP2B3 and CBS-QB3) are near $65\text{--}68 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, while the DFT (B3LYP) calculations are higher with about 77 kcal mol^{-1} .

Table 2: S—O Bond energy in SO_3 in kcal mol^{-1} .

$\text{SO}_3 \rightarrow \text{SO}_2 + \text{O}$	
Method-basis set	BE (kcal mol^{-1})
Literature	83.20 [22]
B3LYP/6-311G(d,p)	77.10
B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p)	74.32
B3LYP/6-311G+(2d,p)	77.4
B3LYP/CBSB7	75.03
BB1K	93.81
B3LYP/LANL2DZ	75.08
CBS-QB3	68.53
G2	68.72
G3	67.29
G3MP2	65.96
G3MP2B3	65.12

2. Kinetic calculations for $\text{SO}_3 \rightarrow \text{SO}_2 + \text{O}^{3p}$

The decomposition of SO_3 is a slow but important reaction and controls the O_2 concentration in the $\text{SO}_3\text{--H}_2\text{O}$ decomposition system [23]. The reaction of SO_3 to SO_2 can also occur under catalytic conditions [6]. Since two TS-structures are identified for SO_3 dissociation, two reaction mechanisms for this dissociation reaction are possible. The reaction rate constants for this unimolecular dissociation reaction have been calculated on the basis of the canonical

transition state theory [24] and listed in Table 3 along with the results of Yilmaz et al. [6] and Zhang et al. [23]. The calculated kinetic parameters for TS-SO3A are in agreement with each other and the activation energy is close to that determined by Yilmaz et al [6]. The structure TS-SO3B results in a lower activation energy. Based on the calculated structure, the parameters obtained with G3 and G3MP2 should be the most accurate. We point out that the high E_a value obtained with G2 confirms that its structure is not appropriate. In general, it seems that the applied methods deliver approximate geometries for TS-structures, which result in large variations of the activation energies. In addition, the reactions could be more complex, particularly the dissociation of SO_3 to $\text{SO}_2 + \text{O}$ may be a sequential reaction. It is also important to point out that all activation energies listed in Table 3 (including experimental values) are lower compared with the S—O bond energy, because they are adjusted to the CHEMKIN format.

Table 3: Kinetic parameters for the reaction $\text{SO}_3 \rightarrow \text{SO}_2 + \text{O}$ in CHEMKIN format

$k = A T^n \exp(-E/RT)$			
Reaction	A	n	E_a
Kinetic parameters for TS-SO3-A (Fig. 2)			
B3LYP/6-311G(d,p)	8.8918E+11	.368	35313
B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p)	1.3476E+12	0.367	36812
B3LYP/6-311G+(2d,p)	1.2989E+12	0.381	33919
G3MP2B3	5.6091E+12	0.156	37330
Kinetic parameters for TS-SO3-B (Fig. 3)			
G3	3.6676E+12	0.480	26434
G3MP2	3.6676E+12	0.480	27104
BB1K/GTLarge	3.7709E+13	0.416	17030
CBS-QB3	2.8326E+12	1.07	15367
B3LYP/CBSB7	2.3349E+13	0.729	14230
Kinetic parameters for TS-SO3 (Fig. 4)			
G2	1.9949E+13	0.968	75080
Kinetic parameters from literature			
Yilmaz et al. [6]	5.70E-17	-	40000
Zhang et al. [23]	3.16E+15	-	63390

AT^n ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$), E (cal mol^{-1})

Reaction of $\text{S}_2 + \text{O}_2$

1. Reaction enthalpy

Reaction enthalpies of the reaction of $\text{S}_2 + \text{O}_2$ relative to the transition state structure (TS-S2O2), has been determined with different levels of calculation. Figures 5-7 and Tables 4-5 show that the identified TS-structures for this reaction depend on the method and level of calculation. The imaginary frequency resulting from B3LYP (including LANL2DZ), G3MP2B3 and CBS-QB3 calculations show clearly the displacement of each oxygen toward each sulfur atom to form two SO (TS2O2A), as illustrated in Figure 5 and Table 4. BB1K enthalpy of reaction is very low compared to other B3LYP calculations and can be explained by the bond lengths of S—O of 2.17 \AA , O—O of 1.22 \AA and S—S

of 1.85 Å. The value of the imaginary frequency (-88.45 cm^{-1}), implies that there is no bond between O_2 and S_2 and this geometry is not a transition state structure. Surprisingly, the best transition state structure can be seen with B3LYP/LANL2DZ level which frequency is -1548.42 cm^{-1} .

Table 4: Relative energy from $\text{S}_2 + \text{O}_2$ to transition state structure TS-S2O2A (to formation of $\text{SO} + \text{SO}$)

$\text{S}_2 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{TS-S2O2A}$		
$\Delta H_{\text{rxn}} (\text{kcal mol}^{-1})$		
Method-basis set	Reaction enthalpy	Bond length of transition state structure in Å
B3LYP/6-311G(d,p)	2.95	O—O (1) = 1.33
B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p)	2.97	S—S (2) = 2.03
B3LYP/6-311G+(2d,p)	0.84	S—O (3) = 2.07
G3MP2B3	7.86	
CBS-QB3	1.52	
BB1K	-60.47	O—O (1) = 1.22 S—S (2) = 1.85 S—O (3) = 2.17
B3LYP/LANL2DZ	-8.20	O—O (1) = 1.37 S—S (2) = 2.33 S—O (3) = 2.09

Figure 5: Structure of TS-S2O2A with (left) B3LYP/LANL2DZ and (right) BB1K. Imaginary frequency = -1548.42 and -88.4492 cm^{-1} respectively.

G3MP2 calculations have shown a different geometry. Figure 6 illustrates the formation of a SSOO compound with a S—O vibrational attraction (TS-S2O2B).

The third structure is obtained with G2, G3 and CBSB7 (TS-S2O2C) as illustrated in Figure 7. We assume a sequential two-step process. The first step is the addition of S_2 and O_2 through TS-S2O2B to form an unstable SSOO which rearranges through TS-S2O2C to form a stable OSSO.

In a previous work [25] we have observed that the G3 calculations with MP2 treat the reaction as sequential reaction. The MP2 “sees” a first barrier (1) in the S—O bond formation, forms an intermediate and rearranges in order to transfer the second oxygen to the S atom (2) over a second barrier. This needs to be evaluated in future work.

Table 5: Relative energy from $\text{S}_2 + \text{O}_2$ to transition state structures TS-S2O2B and TS-S2O2C

$\text{S}_2 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{TS-S2O2B} / \text{TS-S2O2C}$		
$\Delta H_{\text{rxn}} (\text{kcal mol}^{-1})$		
Method-basis set	Reaction enthalpy	Bond length of transition state structure in Å
G3MP2linear SSOO	-3.25	O—O (1) = 1.33 S—S (2) = 1.87 S—O (3) = 1.69
G2	-2.20	O—O = 1.51
G3	-3.95	S—S = 1.93 S—O = 1.66
CBSB7	-13.14	O—O = 1.45 S—S = 2.00 S—O = 1.70

As expected, the relative enthalpies listed in Tables 4 and 5 for the TS-S2O2 structures vary according to the method and the type of structure. Compared with the structure calculated with LANL2DZ, which seems to be the best TS-S2O2A structure, all other B3LYP calculations need higher energy than for TS-S2O2B and TS-S2O2C.

Figure 6: Structure of TS-S2O2B at G3MP2.

Figure 7: Structure of TS-S2O2C at G2, G3 and CBSB7

Reaction of $\text{S}_2 + \text{O}$ to SSO

1. Reaction enthalpy

Reaction enthalpies of $\text{S}_2 + \text{O}$ relative to the transition state structure (TS-SSOA) have been determined with different levels of calculation. As above, the reaction $\text{S}_2 + \text{O} \rightarrow \text{TS-SSO}$ exhibits two possible geometries for the transition states designed TS-SSOA and TS-SSOB.

Figure 8: Structure of TS-SSOA with B3LYP/6311G(d,p), /LANL2DZ and BB1K

The relative energies along with the bond lengths are listed in Table 6. The structures obtained with B3LYP/6-311G(d,p), LANL2DZ and BB1K are illustrated in Figure 8. The oxygen atom is oscillating between the two sulfur atoms. The geometries of the TS-SSOA obtained with the three methods are the same but the bond lengths differ slightly from each other. The influence of the bond lengths on the relative enthalpy is given in Table 6.

Figure 9: Structure of TS-SSOB with G3, G2 and G3MP2

The second transition state structure TS-SSOB, illustrated in Figure 9, is obtained with G2, G3 and G3MP2 and forms SSO. We consider TS-SSOB more likely to be formed than TS-SSOA. The calculations obtained with G2 deliver the best geometry.

Table 6: Relative energy from SSO to transition state structure TS-SSOA and TS-SSOB

<i>TS-SSOA</i> → <i>SSO</i> ΔH_{rxn} (kcal mol ⁻¹)		
<i>Method-basis set</i>	<i>Reaction enthalpy</i>	<i>Bond length of transition state structure</i> Å
B3LYP/6-311G(d,p)	6.20	S—O = 2.05 S—S = 1.92
B3LYP/LANL2DZ	45.27	S—O = 2.40 S—S = 2.06
BB1K	15.66	S—O = 1.95 S—S = 1.89
<i>TS-SSOB</i> → <i>SSO</i> ΔH_{rxn} (kcal mol ⁻¹)		
G3	30.93	S—O = 2.34
G2	37.57	S—S = 1.85
G3MP2	41.36	

Using the enthalpy values of SSO, S₂ and O reported in the literature [22], the S—O bond energy (BE) is calculated to be 103.79 kcal mol⁻¹. The BE calculations of the present work are in good agreement with the literature with ~ 101 kcal mol⁻¹ with B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) and G3. BB1K deviates slightly from literature with 129 kcal mol⁻¹ and B3LYP/LANL2DZ method failed with BE = 71 kcal mol⁻¹. G2 and G3MP2 results have the best agreement with 105.85 and 102.50 kcal mol⁻¹, respectively.

Reaction of SSO to SO + S

1. Reaction enthalpy

The dissociation of SSO to SO and S is more difficult to calculate. Only G3MP2 calculations show a sulfur atom leaving the SSO molecule as illustrated in Figure 10. The S—S distance in the transition structure is 2.99Å

while S—O has already formed the double bond with 1.47Å. G2, G3 and CBS-QB3 calculate the same geometry but the S—S bond at 3.6 Å indicates that it is not a transition state structure but that SO + S are already dissociated. The relative energies for this TS-SO-S is 53 kcal mol⁻¹.

Figure 10: Structure of TS-SO-S with G3MP2

Calculation with all other methods considered in this study, result in a linear structure as illustrated in Figure 11. The S—S distance varies between 2.08 and 2.36 Å. This geometry is very close to the stable SSO and therefore is not considered as a transition state structure.

Figure 11: Structure of TS-SO-S with all methods except G3MP2

Table 7: Standard enthalpies used in this work

Literature standard enthalpy in kcal mol ⁻¹	
S ₂	30.736 ± 0.072 [26]
SO ₂	-70.939 ± 0.048 [26]
SO ₃	-94.591 [27]
SO	1.20 [27]
S	66.245 ± 0.036 [26]
SSO	-13.50 [27]

Also, the S—S bond energy in the SSO molecule based on literature values is found to be at 80.94 kcal mol⁻¹ and only BB1K/GTLarge calculation delivers a similar value of 85.5 kcal mol⁻¹. For all other calculation levels S—S BE estimation is not in agreement with the literature and deviates significantly with 10 to 20 kcal mol⁻¹. These deviations may be explained by the initial geometry. The SSO geometry reported in [22] has an SSO angle of some 120 degrees, while from our calculations the SSO angle is for all methods about 180 degrees. The enthalpy value has to be chosen carefully as well as most of the geometries for this dissociation reaction.

Conclusion

The main objective of this work is to find the most appropriate computational method for the oxidation of S₂ in order to develop a valid reaction mechanism. The reactions of SO₃ → SO₂ + O, S₂ + O₂ → 2SO, S₂ + O → SSO and finally SSO → SO + S have been investigated using several DFT and ab-initio methods. Some results are based on relative

values which are less accurate compared with calculation of the enthalpy of each reactant, intermediate and product along with the transition state structures using isodesmic reactions. We used B3LYP with different basis sets, 6-311G(d,p), 6-311+G(d,p), 6-311+G(2d,p), CBSB7 as well as BB1K/GTLarge (BB95/6-31+G(d,p)). The ab-initio calculations are done with G2, G3, G3MP2, G3MP2B3 and CBS-QB3. The results show that transition state structures vary significantly from method to method. B3LYP calculations should be repeated with higher accuracy like 6-311G+(3df,2p). The LANL2DZ basis set seems to be not appropriate for most of the calculations. From the ab-initio set of methods, G3MP2B3 which geometries are based on B3LYP calculations seems to be inappropriate as well. G3MP2 and G2 and G3 results are more accurate.

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